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Synthesis and photocatalytic performance of magnetic MnFe₂O₄/CdO/ZSM-5 nanocomposite for the degradation of methyl orange (MO) dye

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Abstract

In this research, magnetic MnFe₂O₄/CdO/ZSM-5 catalyst was synthesized via a hydrothermal method for the photodegradation of methyl orange (MO) dye. The structural and magnetic features of the nanocomposite were identified by means of XRD, FESEM, FTIR, EDX, VSM, AFM, and BET. To investigate the photocatalytic activity of the as-synthesized MnFe₂O₄/CdO/ZSM-5 nanocomposite, the H₂O₂-assisted degradation of methyl orange (MO) in water media was evaluated. The results obtained revealed that the ternary MnFe₂O₄/CdO/ZSM-5 nanocomposite had better performance for the photodegradation of MO dye than MnFe₂O₄/CdO, CdO/ZSM-5, MnFe₂O₄/ZSM-5, CdO or MnFe₂O₄. The enhanced photocatalytic activity of the as-synthesized nanocomposite could be related to the rapid production and separation of charge carriers (electrons and holes) in CdO and MnFe₂O₄ and their transfer to the ZSM-5 surface. Plus, magnetic property of MnFe₂O₄ and the relatively high specific surface area of the CdO/ZSM-5 improve the degradation yield of MO dye. The recyclability of the nanocomposite from aqueous solution could be easily gained by an external magnetic field. The impact parameters on the photocatalytic performance like initial MO concentration and catalyst dosage were also investigated. The trapping experiments illustrated that free [•]OH radicals are the main active species in the degradation of MO dye.

Keywords: MnFe₂O₄/CdO/ZSM-5, zeolite, nanocomposite, photocatalyst, MO dye, photodegradation.